

GENE NAME	GENE ID	(5')FORWARD PRIMER(3')	(5')REVERSE PRIMER(3')
<i>NoDGAT1</i>	CCMP1779_3520	GAGCATTCTGCGTCCGTTC	CCCATCTTGACACAGTCGCT
<i>NoDGTT1</i>	CCMP1779_4340	TTATTTGAAATGTGGTGTATTGC	CTGACAGAAGAGACTATGGT
<i>NoDGTT2</i>	CCMP1779_3705	GCTCACCTCTTCCGTCTAG	CGGCTCGATTTCCGGATGAGA
<i>NoDGTT3</i>	CCMP1779_7206	GTCGTGGCTCTTCCGAGAAA	GAGAGGAAGGATACCGTGCG
<i>NoDGTT4</i>	CCMP1779_9929	GGAGATGTTGGTGGAGAG	GTAGTAGTAGTTGTCGTAGCA
<i>NoDGTT5</i>	CCMP1779_3915	CAGCAAAGTTCATGTGG	TAGTAAAGCTCCTCGACCTT
<i>NoDGTT6</i>	CCMP1779_9590	ATGTCCTCCTTCTTGC GTTGGC	GCTATTATTCTTACCGCTGCTACTGC
<i>NoDGTT7</i>	CCMP1779_3159	GGCTGTTCAAGTATCT	CCATTCGTATAAACCTTTCC
<i>NoDGTT8</i>	CCMP1779_358	CCTCACCATCTGCACCTGAG	TGAAGGGGCTTGAAGCAAA
<i>NoDGTT9</i>	CCMP1779_10272	CGTTCGTCTTTGGGGAGGAA	CTTTCCGACGAACGCAACTG
<i>NoDGTT10</i>	CCMP1779_3159	CCGGAAATGTGAGACACGGA	CCCACCACCTCGACTGAAAA
<i>NoDGTT11</i>	CCMP1779_5368	CGGAGCCTTTGTTGTTTCGG	TGAGCCACCAACCAGAATCC
<i>NoDGTT12</i>	CCMP1779_3592	ATATCCGTATGTTGTCAAGGT	GAAGCCGTAGGTGAAGAG
<i>NoACTIN</i>	CCMP1779_1821	GCCGTTATTGGATGGATATG	AACAAGCTCCTTCACA
<i>AtACTIN2</i>	At3g18780	TGTGACAATGGTACCGGTATGG	GCCCTGGGAGCATCATCTC

Table S1. Primers used for reverse transcription quantitative PCR.